

PROCEDURE FOR WORKING SIMPLE TEXT PROBLEMS IN ELEMENTARY GRADES. (IN 3RD GRADE)

Tashboyeva Saidakhan Rahmonberdiyevna

Teacher of Fergana State University
toshboyevasaidaxon@gmail.com

Khojimamatova Khilolakhon Umidjon qizi

Student of Fergana State University
hojimamatovahilola@gmail.com

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ABSTRACT

Textual problems are very important in primary grades. Problems are very helpful for student development and thinking. Any issues that are interesting and attract the student to think will have a more positive effect on his brain activity. For elementary school students, not too complicated, one or two-step problems are recommended. Through them, the scope of thinking expands and serves as a basis for complex issues that will be worked on at the next stages. In order to complete any complex examples and problems, one must first be able to work through simple-looking examples and problems.

Mathematics is a world-class subject that forms the basis for learning all subjects. It was emphasized that it is necessary to increase interest in mathematics among young people, to select talented children, and to organize them into specialized schools and later higher education institutions. The task was set to create popular textbooks and training manuals for children on this subject, written in simple and understandable language, to form the mathematical mind, if necessary, starting from kindergarten.

Mathematics is the basis of all exact sciences. A child who knows this subject well will grow up to be smart, broad-minded, and work successfully in any field, says our president Sh. Mirziyoyev also strongly believes in this science

Indeed, mathematics is considered the king of sciences. This article also contains simple issues that are needed in everyday life. 1st-4th graders should be able to add the price of cheap products at home or when they go to a store, and calculate their price. A person who knows mathematics will never make mistakes in calculations, he knows how much money he has and, most importantly, he can think about when to spend it.

Currently, one of the main tasks of teaching mathematics in elementary schools in schools is to educate students to become mature people in all respects. In this, it is important to provide them with knowledge of mathematics, to ensure that the knowledge they are learning is reasonable and thorough, and to form the skills and abilities to apply it. In particular, the development of thinking abilities in mathematics classes and the formation of necessary skills and competencies for their successful use of the acquired knowledge in conscious life activities in the future should become the main tasks of primary mathematical education.

Solving mathematical problems is an important component of teaching mathematics. It is impossible to imagine mastering mathematics without solving problems. In mathematics, the theory of solving problems is an important way to put it into practice. Solving problems is important in the process of mastering one or another theoretical material studied in primary classes and plays an important role in developing students' thinking skills. Problems are created based on the system of practical cases. This means that the composition of each new concept is always carried out by solving one or another problem that helps to explain the importance of this concept and requires its application. Work on the issue begins with mastering its content. If the condition of the problem is confusing, it is appropriate to give the students one to three minutes to think about the content of the problem independently. Let's pay attention to the analysis of the problems given in the 3rd grade mathematics textbook. In the 3rd grade mathematics textbook, a lot of attention is paid to the ability to write, read and apply numbers.

1. During the summer vacation, Khadija and her brother read 270 fairy tales. 150 of them are Uzbek folk tales, the rest are world folk tales. How many world folk tales have they read?

Given:

Tales - 270

Uzbek folk tales - 150

Need to find: world folk tales - ?

Solution: $270 - 150 = 120$

Answer: 120 world folk tales

2. Zumrad read 120 pages of the 220-page book in the first week, and the rest in the second week. How many more pages did he read in the first week than in the second week?

Given:

Book - 220 pages

In the 1st week - 120 pages

Must find: in week 2 - ?

Solution: $220 - 120 = 100$

Answer: 100 pages in week 2

3. 130 of the 240 watermelons collected in the field were cut from the first furrow and the rest from the second furrow. How many more watermelons were plucked from the first furrow than from the second?

Given:

Total watermelons - 240 pieces

From the 1st groove - 130

Must find: Slot 2 - ?

Solution: $240 - 130 = 110$

Answer: 110

4. A year ago, there were 890 students in the school. 80 of them graduated from school. In the new academic year, 90 students were admitted to the 1st grade. How many students are studying now?

Given:

Total number of students - 890 people

Graduates - 80 people

Accepted - 90 people

Need to find: Total readership?

Solution: 1) $890-80=810$ 2) $810+90=900$

Answer: 900 people

Summary:In conclusion, in order to use the possibilities of innovative methods in the formation of logical thinking in elementary school classes, the essence and content of each concept and its basis on the practical experience of students, as well as the widespread introduction of visualization, comparison, drawing conclusions, in general It is the basis for the creation of similar laws in other actions based on comparison and analysis of exercises and examples, working on mistakes and effective use of all this.

In the process of solving the problem, the problem is fully explained to the students and connected with life. The purpose of this is to get an idea of the problem in the mind of the students. We will also travel to the world of fairy tales to keep the students interested while completing the problem. Only these methods can make the student more interested in science. This is a great achievement of the teacher.

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